

PolarFront May 2022 Cruise Report

Malin Daase (ed.)

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Ship: [R/V Helmer Hanssen](#)

Ecosystem studies using novel autonomous technologies

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Data availability

All data from the PolarFront project are published on [DataverseNO](#).

Introduction

This expedition was the first field phase of the project [Polar Front ecosystem studies using novel autonomous technologies: Knowledge for environmental management and assessing ecological risk](#) (PolarFront). The project elucidates the hydrographical, chemical and biological processes in the Barents Sea Polar Front region. This cruise focused specifically on the highly productive phytoplankton spring bloom period. Associated with the research efforts, UiT students participated in the ARCTOS BIO 8510 course. Financial support for this expedition was provided by the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Equinor and Conoco Philips.

The months of April to June are a period of transitions in the Barents Sea from the dark winter to the bright summer. With the return of the light, the sea ice starts to melt and retreat, and microalgae in ice and water form extensive blooms. Specifically in the water column microscopic microalgae, after months of darkness, show high primary productivity and biomass, providing organic material to all higher trophic levels, from herbivorous zooplankton up to fish, sea birds and whales. The science mission of our expedition explored the biodiversity and biological activity at all trophic levels (from bacteria to whales) along transect lines reaching from relatively warm Atlantic water into the cold Arctic domain. In addition to ship-based sampling, glider and sail buoy applications greatly extended the area, where scientific information had been collected.

After leaving Tromsø on May 18, we started our sampling in Atlantic water at about 75 deg N and extended it across the Polar Front into the ice-covered Arctic waters north of the Front up to 77 deg N. The extensive sea ice cover in 2022 slowed sampling efforts in the northern parts of the area of interest. The scientific efforts concluded with the successful recovery of a glider in stormy seas on May 26. The cruise ended in Tromsø on May 28. The report provides an overview on sampling approaches and first scientific data.

Rolf Gradinger, UiT, cruise leader

Cruise Participants

Name	role	Institute
Rolf Gradinger	cruise leader	UiT
Malin Daase	researcher	UiT
Ronald Berntsen	technician	UiT
John Terje Eilertsen	technician	UiT
Sünnje Basedow	researcher	UiT
Torkel Granaas	master student	UiT
Sunniva	communication	UiT
Anna Miettinen	master student	UiT
Megan Lenss	master student	UiT
Joel Vikberg Wernström	ARCTOS student (PhD)	UiT
Nicolas Gosset	ARCTOS student (PhD)	UiT
Luc Ludovic Nicolas Hallali	ARCTOS student (PhD)	UiT
Paul Renaud	researcher	Akvaplan-niva
Eva Leu	researcher	Akvaplan-niva
Benjamin Merkel	researcher	Akvaplan-niva
Sofia Aniceto	researcher	Akvaplan-niva
Einat Sandbank	PhD student	Memorial University
Maxime Geoffroy	researcher	Memorial University
Emilia Trudnowska	researcher	IOPAN
Fabio Viotti	master student	Akvaplan-niva, ImbrSea
Frida Cnossen	master student	Akvaplan-niva, Univ. Cote D'Azur
Meghan Lightfoot	master student	University of Delaware
Loizos Groutas	engineer	Cyprus Subsea

Group picture (photo: S. Thode)

Study area

The cruise was conducted at the Barents Sea Polar front along a transect following approximately 29.5°E. The first station (PF1) was located in Atlantic water south of the front. From there we steamed northwards mapping the water column with a CTD and LOPC attached to the Moving Vessel Profiler (MVP). We met ice at ca 76°N where we could not continue with the MVP. Instead LOPC/CTD profiles were taken every 5 nm until the ice became too dense to continue (PF2). After sampling at PF2 we turned southward and had full stations at PF3 and PF4. At stations PF2.5 and PF3.5 only CTD, FrrF and a zooplankton net were taken. After we finished at PF4, the ice chart indicated that the ice had broken up following strong southerly winds we experienced over the previous days. Another MVP transect was conducted moving northwards and this time we managed to cross the Polar Front and reached 77°30 N (PF5). On our way south we sampled one last station (PF6).

Figure 1: Study area and sampling stations

Figure 2: Ice charts 23 May 2022. <https://cryo.met.no/>

Figure 3: Ice charts 24 May 2022.

Figure 4: Ice charts 23 and 25 May 2022.

The ice edge (photo: Sunniva Thode)

Research projects

A number of complementary research projects were conducted during the cruise. The Arctos Bio8510 **students** were actively involved in these activities. In this section, descriptions of all research activities have been compiled, together with some preliminary results.

1. Hydrography

Sünnje Basedow, Nicolas Gosset, Torkel Granaas (UiT), Eva Leu (Apn)

Aim

The main aim of the hydrographic measurements taken during the cruise was to identify the position of the polar front and the extent of the meltwater layer, with the overall goal to guide biological sampling by providing information on water masses and fluorescence. These data describe the environment for plankton and fishes and can be used as explanatory variables in later analyses. Ocean current measurements will then also be valuable in calculating transport processes across the front.

Methods

Hydrographic data were collected by a variety of sensors mounted on vertical profiling platforms, towed platforms and autonomous gliders. Combined, these platforms provided detailed information at stations, high-resolution measurements across the polar front, and longer-term measurements by the gliders. During the cruise, hydrographic measurements were taken at stations using the main rosette equipped with 12 5-L Niskin bottles, CTD-F, PAR and other sensors (Table 1.1) and using a smaller rosette frame equipped with CTD-F, LOPC, LISST and WBAT (Table 1.2, Fig. 1.1). Both platforms were deployed vertically until 5-10 m above the bottom for the main platform and down to 300 m for the platform with the LOPC, this rosette sampling three profiles at selected stations.

Fig. 1. The smaller rosette with LOPC, LISST, WBAT EK80, CTD-F at P2. (Picture: Sünnje Basedow)

In total 14 vertical profiles were sampled by the rosette with the water bottles (Table 1.1) at our 6 main stations (PF1 to PF6). Water samples for biological analyses were taken from selected depths and a bottom water samples was collected at each station for calibration of the conductivity sensor ashore. Water samples for chlorophyll a will be used to calibrate the fluorescence sensor. CTD data from this rosette were processed using the SBEDataProcessing-Win32 software. Only the values from the CTD downcast were used to avoid turbulence caused by the rosette on the upcast. The data were converted

to physical units, filtered for outliers and bin-averaged over 1 m bins. CTD data from the smaller rosette were processed using python scripts, using only data from downcasts. Data were filtered for outliers and bin-averaged over 2 Hz.

Table 1.1. Main CTD instruments with serial number and calibration date

Sensor	Serial Number	Calibration date
Conductivity	3016	21 February 2020
Temperature	2512	18 February 2020
Pressure	0780	27 June 2021
Fluorometer	3049	13 March 2008
Turbidity	10854	01 April 2018
PAR	1141	09 December 2017
Oxygen	2557	18 June 2021

In addition to the vertical profiles at stations, hydrographic measurements were also taken by a CTD-F mounted on a moving vessel profiler (MVP), a specialised winch that deploys instruments in a housing ('fish') taking measurements along close-to-vertical profiles before retrieving the instruments again (Fig. 1).

Table 1.2: Overview of deployments

Date	Time (UTC)	Station	Deployment nr.	Latitude N	Longitude E	Depth (m)	LOPC	CTD/F	WBAT	LISST	# profiles
5/20/2022	04:32:28	PF1	743	7500.87	2935.25	373	-	-	x	x	2
5/20/2022	18:25:42	-	746	7557.58	2929.76	299	x	x	x	-	3
5/20/2022	20:12:26	-	747	7602.40	2929.86	309	x	x	x	-	1
5/20/2022	21:42:46	-	748	7606.07	2929.47	304	x	x	x	-	1
5/21/2022	04:48:33	PF2	750	7608.87	2922.00	280	x	x	x	x	3
5/21/2022	12:36:51	-	765	7605.11	2922.41	291	x	x	x	-	3
5/21/2022	16:08:46	-	769	7602.96	2919.46	284	x	x	x	-	1
5/21/2022	17:18:06	-	771	7600.16	2924.31	289	x	x	-	-	3
5/21/2022	19:59:50	-	774	7555.40	2937.52	306	x	x	x	x	1
5/21/2022	22:44:27	-	777	7549.75	2934.59	307	x	x	-	-	3
5/22/2022	00:18:51	-	778	7544.74	2933.00	313	x	x	x	-	3
5/22/2022	01:33:07	-	779	7549.93	2933.10	303	x	x	-	-	3
5/22/2022	06:06:45	PF3	782	7528.54	2935.84	350	-	-	x	x	3
5/22/2022	19:39:05	PF4	803	7459.84	2903.05	362	x	x	x	x	3
5/23/2022	13:14:56	-	818	7510.10	2859.73	347	x	x	-	-	1
5/23/2022	14:36:24	-	819	7520.05	2859.96	340	x	x	x	-	1
5/24/2022	04:33:01	-	821	7642.81	2931.02	248	x	x	-	-	1
5/24/2022	05:32:23	-	822	7648.13	2929.51	267	x	x	-	-	1
5/24/2022	06:36:59	-	823	7652.94	2930.34	257	x	x	x	x	1
5/24/2022	08:00:44	-	824	7658.42	2930.90	237	x	x	-	-	1
5/24/2022	09:10:13	-	825	7703.61	2931.62	218	x	x	x	x	1
5/24/2022	10:03:57	-	826	7707.63	2930.47	208	x	x	-	-	1
5/24/2022	11:11:14	-	827	7712.50	2930.48	203	x	x	x	x	1
5/24/2022	12:18:28	-	828	7717.46	2929.31	183	x	x	-	-	1
5/24/2022	13:34:32	-	829	7722.49	2934.23	188	x	x	x	x	1
5/24/2022	15:09:29	-	830	7727.59	2949.26	202	x	x	-	-	1
5/24/2022	16:19:04	PF5	832	7729.52	2951.63	196	x	x	x	x	3
5/25/2022	11:50:32	PF6	866	7701.06	2941.58	234	x	x	x	x	1

Table 1.3: Overview of samples taken

Date	Time (UTC)	Station nr.	Deployment nr.	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)	depths for water sampling	Chl a	POC/N	SI POM	FCM	taxonomy	nutrients	FRRf	¹⁴ C PP	Bacterial production	Optodes	SI incubations
5/19/22	21:24	P1	729	7500.60	2930.28	373	no water samples											
5/19/22	23:24	P1	733	7500.47	2930.72	371	5-20-bottom	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	
5/20/22	1:20	P1	738	7500.53	2932.09	372	10-50-100	x	x		x	x	x	x				
5/21/22	5:58	P2	752	7609.10	2922.82	282	5-25-bottom	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
5/21/22	7:59	P2	757	7609.54	2924.63	287	10-50-100	x	x		x	x	x	x				
5/22/22	7:18	P3	783	7528.53	2937.82	353	5-20-bottom	x	x		x	x	x	x				
5/22/22	9:14	P3	787	7528.03	2941.98	355	10-50-100	x	x		x	x	x	x				
5/22/22	17:50	P4	800	7459.96	2900.97	360	no water samples											
5/23/22	6:04	P4	806	7459.97	2901.46	359	5-20-bottom	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
5/23/22	7:11	P4	808	7459.75	2903.14	362	10-50-100	x	x		x	x	x	x				
5/24/22	17:02	P5	833	7729.92	2951.25	196	5-20-bottom	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
5/24/22	18:25	P5	837	7730.55	2952.17	197	10-50-100	x	x		x	x	x	x				
5/25/22	6:16	P6	851	7702.02	2931.78	229	5-30-bottom	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				x
5/25/22	9:09	P6	858	7701.27	2935.46	226	10-50-100	x	x		x	x	x	x				

P1: nutrients only 1 replicate; other parameters duplicates

FCM: not taken from bottom

SI POM: natural concentrations of stable isotopes in POM- from Chla max only

FRRf: only four depths: 5-10-Chla max-50; maximum yield + one FLC (rapid light curve)

¹⁴C primary production: only from 5m and Chl a max; 3 hours

Bacterial production: only from 5m and Chla max; 3H Leucin; 2 hours

Optodes: from Chla max and 5m; at least 24 hours

SI incubations: two parallel settings (in triplicates): ¹⁵NO₃ + ¹³C; ¹⁵NH₄+¹³C/ only from Chla max; 24 h

This procedure is repeated while the ship moves at 6-7 knots, resulting in a high spatial resolution of measurements. MVP-CTD-F data were collected at two transects trying to cross the polar front from south to north (Table 4). When weather conditions (high waves) or ice prohibited sampling with the MVP, (free wheel mode), sampling was completed with vertical profiles with the small rosette. This was the case on the end of transect 1 (ice) and the beginning (high waves) and end (ice) of transect 2. CTD data were processed as described above, using python scripts. To calibrate the fluorometer in the ‘fish’ against filtered chlorophyll seawater from the seawater intake (ca. 7 m) was collected when the ‘fish’ was at that depth (n = 23). Those samples have partly been analysed on board and will partly be analysed ashore at UiT.

Ocean current measurements were taken by an ADCP (75kHz) and were recorded (blanking distance 8 m, bottom track on) during our entire study from 18-26 May. Data are stored at UiT.

Table 1.4: Start and end of MVP sections

		Date	UTC	Latitude	Longitude
S1	start	2022-05-20	06:57:00	74.993	29.535
	end	2022-05-20	16:16:00	75.894	29.916
S2	start	2022-05-23	16:03:00	75.407	28.991
	end	2022-05-24	03:43:00	76.722	29.5

Preliminary results

Figure 1.2: Salinity (top) and temperature (bottom) at section 1 (S1, left) and 2 (S2, right). Tick marks on top indicate sampled profiles, where they are relatively wide apart sampling was done with the small rosette, else with the MVP.

Atlantic influenced water masses ($S > 34.8$) dominated our transects. During our first sampling (20th May) from South to North, dense ice cover prevented us from crossing the Polar Front. A melt water layer with low salinity and temperature overlay the thick Atlantic water masses. This layer was gradually deepening toward the North. A few days later, during our second sampling (23/24th May), the wind had pushed the ice further north and we were able to just cross the Polar Front, as clearly seen by the abrupt change in salinity and temperature. Polar Water occupied the entire water column in the North, and likely also the surface water with slightly higher salinity (ca. 34.2), but cold temperatures can be identified as Polar Water. T/S diagrams will be created to clearly identify water masses when all sensors have been inter-calibrated.

Fluorescence at S2 indicate surface maxima in Atlantic and Polar Water but subsurface maxima in the meltwater layer (Fig. 1.3).

Figure 1.3: Fluorescence along S2. Note the different scale. Both sensors show un-calibrated values, left analog values from the MVP fluorometer, right values from the fluorometer on the smaller rosette.

2. Water sampling, phytoplankton and production rate measurements

Eva Leu (Apn), Joel Vikberg Wernstorm, Megan Lenss, Rolf Gradinger, Anna Miettinen (UiT)

The Phytoplankton group collected different water samples from the Niskin bottles attached to the rosette with the Conductivity, Temperature and Depth (CTD) sensor. Those samples are analysed for various parameters including Chlorophyll- a (Chl-a), nutrients, taxonomy, flow cytometry, Particulate Organic Carbon/Nitrogen (POC/PON), Dissolved Organic Carbon (DIC), and maximum photosynthetic yield determined by Fast Repetition Rate fluorometry (FRRf). The CTD sampling was performed in two casts at each station, the first collecting water from close to the bottom, depth of maximum in situ Chl a fluorescence and 5 m. The second cast was used to collect water from 100, 50, and 10 m depth. Depending on the nature of water parameters and protocols, some of the water samples from the Niskin bottles at each CTD station were directly collected in labelled bottles and tubes, i.e. Chl-a, POC, Taxonomy, while the remaining were first filtered to avoid contamination and then stored in the labelled bottles, for example, CDOM and nutrients (Table 2.1). Among the list of variables shown in Table.2.1, Chl-a was analyzed onboard. The remaining samples were stored frozen (or cooled) to be processed later at UiT – The Arctic University of Norway. Further details are provided in the methodology section.

Table 2.1. Overview of the water parameters measured with their procedures, storage and importance.

Variable	Filter	Container	Storage	Importance
Chl-a	GF/F (25 mm)	Polycarbonate vials; 7 / 10 ml 90% acetone	4°C; dark for 12-24 hours prior to extraction	Serves as proxy for phytoplankton biomass
Nutrients	Burnt GF/F (25 mm), Swinnex, syringe	15 ml Falcon tube	-20°C; dark	Concentrations of inorganic macronutrients available in the water
Taxonomy 60 ml	None	Brown glass bottle (60 mL; 1% formaldehyde (1.5-2 mL) 5ml Parafilm	4°C; dark	Identify the species and communities of Phytoplankton.
Flow Cytometry	None	4 ml cryovials, 20 µL of glutaraldehyde	-80°C; Ziploc	Number and size of cells in a water sample. Differentiate algal and bacteria.
POC/PON	Burnt GF/F (25 mm)	Burnt tinfoil pocket; (fold edges twice); label before the filter	-20°C	Essential trace elements (micronutrients) in the water columns.
DIC	None	Exetainer 20 ul HgCL	4°C; dark	It is a form of CO ₂ and quantifies how much inorganic carbon is available for photosynthesis.

Chlorophyll-a

by Joel Vikberg Wernström

Water samples for chlorophyll-a measurements were taken at defined depths using a Niskin bottle rosette. A vacuum pump system and glass microfiber papers with a mesh size of 0.7 μm were used for filtering the samples, and the volume of water (Table 2.2) necessary for acquisition of sufficient amounts of chlorophyll was gauged throughout the process. Two replicates of each sample were processed for the station PF1. For the remaining stations three replicates per sample were processed. After filtration, filter papers were removed with a forceps and deposited in individually labelled plastic tubes inside a fridge for chlorophyll-a extraction in 7-10 mL of 90% acetone overnight.

Table 2.2. Overview of depths where samples of chlorophyll-a were taken at each location, and the volume filtered for each sample.

PF1 (m)	Volume filtered (L)	PF2 (m)	Volume filtered (L)	PF3 (m)	Volume filtered (L)	PF4 (m)	Volume filtered (L)	PF5 (m)	Volume filtered (L)	PF6 (m)	Volume filtered (L)
5	0.5	5	0.25	5	0.25	5	0.25	5	0.25	5	0.25
10	0.4	10	0.25	10	0.2	10	0.25	10	0.25	10	0.25
20	0.5	25	0.1	20	0.2	20	0.25	20	0.25	20	0.25
50	0.5	50	0.5	50	0.5	50	0.5	50	0.4	50	0.4
100	0.5	100	0.5	100	0.5	100	0.5	100	0.5	100	1
360	1	270	0.75	341	0.5	346	0.5	184	0.5	216	0.75

Following overnight extraction, samples were taken out of the fridge appx 10 minutes before fluorescence measurements to attain room temperature. Fluorescence measurements were carried out using a fluorometer and a fluorometric acidification method. Each acetone solution was transferred to a glass cuvette by pouring and placed in the fluorometer, after which the fluorometer readout in volts was noted. Subsequently, the cuvette was taken out of the instrument and 3 drops of 5% HCl were added, followed by covering the cuvette opening with a piece of clean parafilm and gentle mixing. The sample was then placed back in the fluorometer and the new readout was written down. This process was repeated for each sample and replicate.

Chla measurements onboard with a Turner fluorometer.

Preliminary results of chlorophyll-a measurements

Generally, the chlorophyll-a fluorescence values indicated that the primary production was most intense at the two stations PF2 and PF3 in the upper 20-25 meters of the water column (Fig. 1) in response to a clear stratification pattern caused by cold and less saline meltwater on top. In the two southernmost stations (PF1 and PF4), the water column was relatively well mixed after some storms, and the phytoplankton biomass was rather evenly distributed over the uppermost 80-100m of the water column. In the very northernmost stations (PF5 and PF6), the bloom appeared less intense and had likely not yet reached its peak at the time of sampling. PF6 was the only station with a distinct sub-surface Chla

maximum at about 30m depth. Throughout all remaining stations, the chlorophyll-max depth was similar - between 20-25 meters - and at the bottom only very low concentrations of chlorophyll were present at all stations.

Figure 2.1. Chlorophyll-a concentrations measured from water samples taken at six depths at each station.

Nutrients

The water samples were directly taken with a sterile syringe and vinyl gloves to avoid contamination from the Niskin bottles for nutrients. A Swinnex filter holder with a burnt GF/F (25mm) filter was attached to the acid-washed syringe. After rinsing the filter and the containers, the water was then filtered in three replicates into 15 ml centrifuge tubes for each depth, respectively. The samples were then stored at -20°C until further analysis on return to land.

Taxonomy

For species composition analysis samples were collected from the CTD. From each depth, 60 ml of water were filled into a labelled brown glass bottle. 1.5-2 ml of formaldehyde was added to each sample and stored in darkness at 4°C for later analysis by light microscopy.

Flow Cytometry

Water samples will be the measurement for bacteria and algae abundance using Flow Cytometry. In preparation for this, duplicates of each sample, one for bacteria and one for algae, were made ready. Two 5 ml cryovials were filled with 3.5-4 ml of a sample before adding 20 µL of glutaraldehyde (25% or higher) in each tube. Samples were then frozen at -80°C.

POC/PON

At each station water collected for POC/PON measurements was filtered in three replicates through pre-combusted (for 6 hours at 450°C) GF/F (25mm) filters with the aid of a low vacuum pressure pump. The volume (250-1000 mL, depending on phytoplankton abundances) for each replicate and the time needed for filtering was noted down. The bottles and funnels were rinsed with filtered seawater after each sample. The filters were then folded and individually packed in burned tinfoil, packaged in plastic zip bags and stored at -20°C until analysis in the lab on return.

DIC

Total dissolved inorganic carbon measures the sum of bicarbonate, carbonate and carbonic acid and dissolved CO₂. Here DIC was taken as a reference measurement for spike and incubation measurements with C¹⁴; therefore, the samples were taken according to this. For DIC and the C¹⁴ incubation, seawater was taken from 5m and the depth corresponding to the chlorophyll maximum of each sampling station, respectively and filled into air-tight containers. From this, 10 vials for C¹⁴ incubations with 60ml each were taken by a syringe. Additionally, for DIC measurements, 12ml were taken in duplicates with a glass syringe from the same container and filled into exetainers for later analysis in UiT. To these exetainers, 20µl HgCl were added under strict safety standards. Each exetainer was then stored at 4°C in the dark until analysis on land.

Primary, net community and bacterial production

By Megan Lenss, UiT

Bacterial production, primary production, and net community production was measured on water samples collected from surface water and chlorophyll-*a* maximum using the rosette at the northern and southern ends of the parallel cross-frontal transects (P1, P2, P4, and P5).

Bacterial production

1.5 mL subsamples were measured into four Eppendorf tubes and inoculated with a ³H-Leucine working solution. 100% trichloroacetic acid was added to one tube to use as a blank. Samples were incubated for two hours in darkness at *in-situ* temperatures as determined by the CTD. 100% trichloroacetic acid was then added to all tubes. Further sample processing and scintillation counting will take place at UiT after the cruise. See Simon & Azam (1989) for details on incubation methodology.

Primary production

60 mL subsamples were measured into 10 clear and two dark incubation flasks (*Corning*) with the latter containing di-chloromethyl urea. Each bottle was inoculated with a ¹⁴C working solution and incubated for three hours in temperature-controlled PI chambers set to *in-situ* temperatures as measured by the CTD. Samples were then filtered onto GF/F (*Whatmann*). Filters were acidified with 0.5N HCl and dried before addition of 10 mL Ecolume scintillation cocktail. Scintillation counting will take place at UiT after the cruise. See Campbell et al. (2016) for details on incubation methodology.

Net community production

Samples were incubated using the oxygen-optode set-up presented in Campbell et al. (2016) modified to accommodate four 100 mL glass bottles (*Wheaton*). Bottles were filled with sample using a peristaltic pump to avoid bubble and head-space formation. Each bottle was fitted with a one-centimeter magnetic stir bar and robust optode probe (*Firesting*) that continually logged oxygen at two second intervals over a period of approximately 24 hours. All samples were placed in temperature-controlled incubation chambers set to *in-situ* temperatures as measured by the CTD. Samples were exposed to light set to *in-situ* intensities as measured by the CTD, with the surface sample receiving a higher light intensity than the chlorophyll-*a* maximum sample. Samples were allowed to equilibrate in the chamber for a minimum of 2 hours in darkness and all probes were calibrated to 0 and 100% oxygen prior to incubations.

Phytoplankton photophysiology measured by Fast Repetition Rate fluorometry (FRRf)

By Eva Leu

In order to gain more detailed information about the physiological state of the different phytoplankton communities we encountered on the cruise, water samples from the Niskin bottles were taken for analysis by Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometry. This technique allows to measure in a controlled benchtop-approach maximum photosynthetic yield of dark-acclimated microalgae, which gives indications about potential stress. In addition, Fast Light Curves (FLC) were measured, which provide information about the photoacclimation state of algae.

These analyses were carried out at all 6 main sampling stations (PF1-PF6), usually from four different depths: 5-10-Chla max-50m.

Table 2.3: Overview of locations and sampling depths where photosynthetic yield and Fast Light Curves (FLCs) were measured.

Depth [m]	PF1	PF2	PF3	PF4	PF5	PF6
5	X	X	X	X	X	X
10	X	X	X	X	X	X
Chla max	X (20m)	X (25m)	X (20m)	X (20m)	X (20m)	X (30m)
50	X	X	X	X	X	X

Preliminary results show high yield values at most stations and depths, indicating well-growing algae in favourable conditions. At the stations with the strongest stratification, however, maximum photosynthetic yield was lower in the surface samples, which indicates some sort of stress. FLC data need to be quality-checked and re-fitted before final results will be available.

In addition to measuring field samples from all stations, four experiments were carried out in which natural algae communities were transferred to different types of water (collected on the cruise) to study their response to this change in environmental conditions over the course of 38, 55 and 66 hours, respectively. For an overview of the exact treatments and origins of phytoplankton communities, see Table 2.4. Phytoplankton communities were collected with a 20 μm phytoplankton net from 30-0 m at the respective station. Filtered seawater was obtained by GF/F filtration of water samples from the respective stations.

Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometer used for photophysiological measurements

Table 2.4: Overview of treatment combinations in experiments I-IV

	code	Phytoplankton community origin	Treatment 0	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Measurements
I	PF1_2	Atlantic community (PF1)	PF1 5m FSW	PF2 5m FSW	PF2 bottom FSW	aborted
II	PF2_1	Arctic community (PF2)	PF2 5m FSW	PF1 5m FSW	PF1 bottom FSW	27-48-66 hours
III	PF5_4	Arctic community (PF5)	PF5 5m FSW	PF4 5m FSW	PF4 bottom FSW	15-35-55 hours
IV	PF6_4	Arctic meltwater community (PF6)	PF6 10m FSW	PF4 5m FSW	PF4 bottom FSW	24-40 hours

Experiment I was aborted after the 48 hours, as no measurable yield was found in any of the treatments. Incubations were carried out in an incubator at 3°C and irradiances of about 49-60 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in continuous light. Flasks were re-positioned about 2-3 times a day and sampled and measured in randomized order.

Overview of start of experiment I: transferring an Atlantic phytoplankton community to different types of FSW.

Samples were taken initially and at the end of the experiment for Chla concentrations and species compositions, as well as POC/N (only experiments III/IV). In addition, maximum photosynthetic yield was measured at three occasions: after 27/48/66, 15/35/55 hours and after 24 and 40 hours, respectively, for experiments II, III and IV.

The laboratory-based FRRf measurements will be compared to the continuous *in situ* profiles with another FRRf that were carried out at multiple stations (see below). Comparing those with the controlled measurements of dark-acclimated yield from discrete sampling depths will provide valuable information about the potential and limitations of applying this technique *in situ*.

Incubator with two experiments ongoing.

Nitrate and ammonium uptake rates (measured using enriched stable isotopes)

Eva Leu (Akvaplan-niva)

From stations PF5 and PF6, nitrate and ammonium uptake rates were measured for water samples taken at the depth of maximum Chl a concentration (20m at PF5 and 30m at PF6). These measurements were carried out using solutions of $\text{Na}^{15}\text{NO}_3$ and $^{15}\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ in three replicates each. In addition to the enriched nitrogen isotopes, I added as well $\text{NaH}^{13}\text{CO}_3$ to determine inorganic carbon uptake during the incubations. Water samples were incubated in 400 mL culture flasks shortly after sampling (within 1 hour) and spiked with 400 μl of the working stock solutions (containing 0.1 $\mu\text{g-at NO}_3\text{-N/mL}$ and 0.1 $\mu\text{g-at NH}_4\text{-N/mL}$, as well as 100 $\mu\text{g-at DIC/mL}$, respectively). The flasks were placed in an incubator at 4.5 °C and irradiances of 50 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ for 24 hours. After this, they were filtered on pre-combusted (6 hours, 450°C) GF/F filters and frozen at -20°C until further analyses.

Phytoplankton composition

Rolf Gradinger (UiT)

A preliminary assessment of the phytoplankton composition at the stations PF1-6 was done based on 20 μm net plankton samples collected from 30m water depths to the surface at each station. A small subsample (ca. 3ml) was filled into an Utermoehl chamber and analysed within 1.5 hours after sampling to provide first insights into species diversity.

All samples were dominated by diatom species typical for Barents Sea spring blooms including several *Thalassiosira* species and *Chaetoceros gelidus*. Additionally, *Phaeocystis pouchetii* contributed in various extend at all stations. Heterotrophic dinoflagellates of the genera *Gyrodinium* and *Protoperidinium* were abundant at all stations, while ciliates were rarely seen. At on station (PF1), the colonial choanoflagellate *Parvicorbicula socialis* was medium abundant, but not observed at the other stations. The northernmost station in ice cover showed in addition several typical Arctic ice algal species in the water column, among them *Nitzschia frigida* and a relatively higher abundance of ciliates and tintinnids, while *Phaeocystis pouchetii* was not observed.

In situ FRRF deployments

Rolf Gradinger (UiT)

A downward looking FRRF (Chelsea, Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometer) was deployed at all main stations (Appendix I). The FRRF was mounted in a frame together with a CASTAWAY CTD. Recordings were done ca every 0.5m depth over the uppermost 90m of the water column (for example see Fig. 2.2). Profiles followed two main patterns. Several station like PF1 showed a very homogenous vertical profile of the ambient variable fluorescent yield, indicating little quenching even in the surface layers, while other stations like PF2 showed low yields in the surface layers likely due to combined effects of light related quenching and nutrient limitation (to be determined).

Further data exploration will include linking the ambient FRRF measurements with water column hydrography, in-situ irradiance, nutrient concentrations, algal abundances and the algal activity measurements using onboard FRRF (Eva Leu) and productivity incubations (Megan Lens).

Fig. 2.2: Examples of vertical profiles of the ambient variable fluorescent yields at station PF1 (SL735) and PF2 (SL749). Depth (m) on x axis, variable fluorescent yield on y-axis.

Deploying the FRRf (photo: Sunniva Thode)

3. Zooplankton size structure, composition, distribution and production

Malin Daase, Sünnje Basedow, Torkel Graanas, Nicholas Gosset (UiT), Emilia Trudnowska (IOPAN)

We used a number of different nets as well as optical sensors to determine the distribution patterns and species composition, abundance and biomass of the different size classes of the zooplankton community in the study area.

Copepods of the genus *Calanus* are key species in the energy transfer between primary producers and higher trophic levels and often dominate the mesozooplankton community in the Arctic and sub-Arctic Barents Sea. To estimate their production and lipid content, we measured egg production rates and measured the population lipid content in the study area.

Mesozooplankton species composition, abundance, biomass

To determine the mesozooplankton community composition, abundance and vertical distribution, a Multinet (MPS) (HydroBios Kiel, 180 µm, 0.25 m² opening area) was deployed at each main station. Samples were taken from 5 standard depth strata (bottom- 200-100-50-20-0 m) and fixed in 4% formalin in seawater solution. These samples will be analysed for community and *Calanus* stage composition at UiT. To estimate the biomass of the mesozooplankton community a WP2 net (HydroBios Kiel, 180 µm, 0.25 m² opening area) was taken from the entire water column. The sample was size fractionated into a 1000 µm and 180µm fraction by pouring it through a 1000 and 180 µm sieve. Each sample was rinsed with fresh water and placed in a pre-weighted weighing dish and dried at 60°C in the drying oven. The dried samples were weighted back at UiT.

Table 3.1: Overview of samples taken for community analysis and dry weight

Station #	Location	Date	Sample depth	Gear	type	stored
734	PF1	19.05.2022	352-200-100-50-20-0	MPS	Community	4% formalin
753	PF2	21.05.2022	262-200-100-50-20-0	MPS	Community	4% formalin
784	PF3	22.05.2022	335-200-100-50-20-0	MPS	Community	4% formalin
802	PF4	22.05.2022	342-200-100-50-20-0	MPS	Community	4% formalin
834	PF5	24.05.2022	178-100-50-20-0	MPS	Community	4% formalin
855	PF6	25.05.2022	200-100-50-20-0	MPS	Community	4% formalin
775	PF2.5	21.05.2022	290-0	WP2	Community	4% formalin
798	PF3.5	22.05.2022	330-0	WP2	Community	4% formalin
739	PF1	20.05.2022	360-0	WP2	Biomass	Dried
756	PF2	21.05.2022	260-0	WP2	Biomass	Dried
791	PF3	22.05.2022	350-0	WP2	Biomass	Dried
801	PF4	22.05.2022	345-0	WP2	Biomass	Dried
838	PF5	24.05.2022	180-0	WP2	Biomass	Dried
860	PF6	25.05.2022	219-0	WP2	Biomass	Dried

Stable isotopes

Samples for stable isotopes were taken at station PF4 and PF5. Individuals were picked from the WP3 nets. See Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Overview of samples taken for stable isotope analysis

Station	species	stage	# ind	# replicates	frozen -20
PF4	<i>C. fin</i>	AF	30	3	x
PF4	<i>C. hyp</i>	CV	10	1	x
PF4	<i>M. longa</i>	AF	30	3	x
PF4	<i>T. longicaudata</i>		3	3	x
PF5	<i>C. fin</i>	AF	30	3	x
PF5	<i>C. gla</i>	AF	30	3	x
PF6	<i>C. fin</i>	AF	30	1	x

Calanus population lipid content

To estimate the lipid content of the *Calanus* community, a WP3 (1000 μm mesh size, 1 m^2 opening) was deployed from bottom to surface. Samples were transferred into a measuring beaker and concentrated to a certain volume. The sample was transferred into a measuring beaker and filled with filtered sea water to a known volume (400–600 mL, depending on density of the sample). Quantitative subsamples were taken with a 5 mL pipette with an enlarged opening and transferred into a petri dish. Digital images (lateral view) were taken of all *Calanus* (living and dead) in each subsample using a Leica stereomicroscope with a camera (Leica DFC420). Subsample size was chosen to contain at least 100 *Calanus* from each sample. Copepodite stage of each individual was determined while taking the pictures. The digital images were used to measure lipid sac area, prosome length and prosome area of specimens using ImageJ, an open source graphics program (Rasband 1997–2009). Lipid content of individual *Calanus* specimens was calculated from lipid sac area according to Vogedes et al. (2010). At PF6 the wind condition did not allow to deploy the WP3 net, and samples for lipid content analyses were instead taken with the WP2 net (0.25 m^2 , 180 μm mesh size).

Table 3.3: overview of samples taken for lipid image analysis

Station #	Location	Date	sample depth	gear
740	PF1	20.05.2022	360	WP3
758	PF2	21.05.2022	260	WP3
776	PF2.5	21.05.2022	290	WP3
793	PF3	22.05.2022	350	WP3
813	PF4	23.05.2022	360	WP3
840	PF5	24.05.2022	190	WP3
863	PF6	25.05.2022	220	WP2

Preliminary results and observations

Zooplankton abundance was overall very low, especially at PF1-PF4, and PF6 (stations in Atlantic waters). In Arctic waters (PF5), abundance was noticeable higher due to the presence of larger Arctic *Calanus* species. From the image analysis we get a preliminary estimate of the *Calanus* abundance (Figure 3.1) at the different stations as well as an estimate of the population lipid content (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.1: Abundance and species composition of the *Calanus* population across the Polarfront. f= *C. finmarchicus*, g= *C. glacialis*, h= *C. hyperboreus*

Figure 3.2: Total lipid (TL) content of *Calanus* population across the Polarfront. f= *C. finmarchicus*, g= *C. glacialis*, h= *C. hyperboreus*

CVs and females dominated the *Calanus* community in the WP3 nets. Due to string winds, we used a WP2 net (0.25 m², 180 μm) at PF6 to pick *Calanus* for experiments, and here younger stages (CII and CIII) that are not caught quantitatively with the WP3 were also abundant, indication that reproduction was ongoing. Females were found at all stations and produced eggs (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: *Calanus* stage composition of f= *C. finmarchicus*, g= *C. glacialis*, h= *C. hyperboreus*. Note that abundance of *C. glacialis* and *C. hyperboreus* at PF1-4 was very low, i.e. data is based on few individuals. At PF6 samples were taken with WP2 net which explains the high contribution of young copepodite stages (CI-CIII).

Multinet flushing (photo: S. Thode)

Egg and faecal pellet production

At selected stations an additional WP3 net was taken to pick out individual *Calanus* for egg and faecal pellet production incubations. To estimate the faecal pellet production of *Calanus* CVs, 12-20 individuals were placed in individual incubation chambers with false bottoms. The chambers were filled with filtered sea water and *Calanus* were incubated for 24 hours inside the cold room ($\sim 4^{\circ}\text{C}$). After 24 hours, the incubation was stopped by removing the individuals from the incubation chambers. Live individuals were photographed for subsequent lipid content estimation. The number of faecal pellet produced in each chamber was counted under a stereomicroscope.

To measure egg *Calanus* egg production, females of *Calanus* (around 20 individuals per species, if present) were placed in individual incubation chambers with false bottoms. The chambers were filled with filtered sea water and *Calanus* were incubated for 24 hours inside the cold room ($\sim 4^{\circ}\text{C}$). After 24 hours, the incubation was stopped by removing the individuals from the incubation chambers. Live individuals were photographed for subsequent lipid content estimation. The number of eggs produced in each chamber was counted under a stereomicroscope.

Table 3.4: overview of samples taken for faecal pellet production and egg production rates incubations

Station #	Location	Date	gear	sample depth	Faecal pellet production	Egg production
742	PF1	20.05.2022	WP3	360	x	x
760	PF2	21.05.2022	WP3	100	x	x
792	PF3	22.05.2022	WP3	350	-	X
814	PF4	23.05.2022	WP3	360	x	x
839	PF5	24.05.2022	WP3	190	x	X
861	PF6	25.05.2022	WP2	220	-	X

Preliminary observations: *Calanus* with green guts were observed at all stations, but the number of faecal pellets produced during the faecal pellet incubations were low, indicating methodological problems (Figure 3.4). *Calanus* did produce eggs and analysis of the egg production rates in comparison with production estimates from the LOPC data will be conducted by master student Torkel Graanas.

Figure 3.4: Proportion of *Calanus* at each station with green guts (based on image analysis). g= green gut; n= nothing in gut

Laser Optical Plankton Counter - spatial zooplankton distribution Sünnje Basedow, Nicolas Gosset

The aim of the LOPC measurements was (i) to create spatial distribution patterns of plankton (ca. in the range of small copepods to juvenile krill) with high resolution (WP1) and (ii) to create biovolume spectra based on which a number of rates can be estimated, including growth and secondary production (WP2). These estimates will be refined based on data collected at the stations. In particular, we aim to create combined spectra based on data from the LISST (1-500 μm , Emilia Trudnowska), LOPC (250 μm to 3 mm) and single targets from the EK80 (fish, Maxime Geoffroy).

Methods

The same LOPC was mounted on two platforms, the MVP and the smaller rosette (together with LISST and WBAT), and thus collected data along transects as well as at stations to allow for inter-comparison. Data were roughly processed on board for selected size groups, further analyses will be completed at UiT.

Preliminary results

Figure 3.5. Distribution of larger zooplankton (juvenile krill and larger) along section 1.

Along the first transect (S1), only a few patches of higher abundance of larger plankton were observed, while abundances along most of the transect were very low. Data for zooplankton have not yet been processed for transect 2.

Counting eggs (Photo: S. Thode)

Laser In-Situ Scattering and Transmissometry (LISST)

Emilia Trudnowska, IOPAN

Aim:

- To provide profiles of vertical distribution of small size fractions of plankton (3-500µm)
- To provide an analysis of size structure of small size fractions of plankton (3-500µm)
- To supplement estimation of productivity of the studied systems based on size spectra theory

Method

A particle size analyser - LISST (**L**aser **I**n-**S**itu **S**cattering and **T**ransmissometry) was used at XX station in a manner of vertical profiles of the upper 300m in combination with LOPC, VBat and CTD rosette platform. The LISST-100X instrument is a laser diffraction device. It consists of optics for producing a collimated laser beam, a specially constructed detector array, electronics for signal pre-amplification and processing, data storage and scheduling computer, and a battery system. The principal measurement—angular scattering distribution—is obtained over 32 ring-detectors whose radii increase logarithmically from 102 to 20,000 microns. This angular range corresponds, respectively, to size ranges from 2.5 to 500 µm (Type C). It belongs to the consortium of PAN (Polish Academy of Sciences) and was brought to the cruise by Emilia Trudnowska, who is also responsible for data collection and processing.

The laser diffraction method for sizing particles was invented in the 1970's and rapidly became the most widely used optical method for determining size distribution for the simple reason that for laser diffraction, the composition or refractive index of the particles is not important. This method determines size distribution of an ensemble of particles. According to preliminary data analyses, we could observe distinct particle distribution patterns as well as size distribution between southernmost and northernmost stations.

Preliminary results

In the case of the southernmost station (PF1) of the 1st transect, the particles, presumably mostly phytoplankton, occurred at really low (<3) concentrations and had rather even distribution within the upper 100 m. Then, peak concentration of particles occurred at the very upper layer at the intermediate station (PF3), where meanwhile the peak was the highest among the volume concentrations observed during the whole cruise (30). Northwards (T1 (774), PF2 stations), the volume concentrations of particles dropped by app. half and the location of their peak shifted slightly deeper, resulting in a kind of a subsurface peak (Fig. 3.6). Such subsurface peak of similar range of the concentration was observed also at the last investigated station (PF6).

Figure 3.6. Vertical profiles of total volume concentration of particles assessed via LISST along the 1st section plus PF6 station (note the X-scale differences).

Also a size structure of particles differed among the stations located along the first section (Fig. 3.7). The interesting, mostly 2-modal (peaks at 5 μ m and 30 μ m) distribution pattern was observed at the southernmost station (PF1). Whereas the volume concentration of particles at the intermediate station (PF3) was mostly shifted towards the smallest size fractions (peaks at 3 μ m and 5 μ m) with a slight accumulation of volume concentration also at the end of the analysed size spectrum. Similarly, this slight peak of particles of the size of app. 330 μ m was observed at the northernmost station (PF2), co-occurring with the most pronounced peak oscillating around 5 μ m size (Fig. 3.7). At the PF6 station the highest volume concentration was observed within the smallest size class (3 μ m), with a gradually decreasing trend towards larger size fractions.

Figure 3.7: A size structure of particles assessed via LISST at the stations of the 1st section. Y axis: Volume concentrations within 32 size classes normalised to the widths of the size classes. X axis: log(size class)

The southernmost station of the 2nd section (PF4) was, similarly as PF1, characterized by generally low, but slightly elevated and rather uniform distribution of volume concentration of particles within the upper 100m (Fig. 8). An interesting, bi-modal vertical distribution pattern of particles was observed at the first intermediate station of this section (T2 (823)), whereas a strong subsurface peak was observed 10nm further north (T3 (825) station. At two next intermediate stations (T4 (827) & T5 (829), app 10 nm distance among them) no specific peak of volume concentration of particles could be distinguished. Whereas a very pronounced volume concentration peak was observed at the northernmost station (PF5). At each of the stations of the 2nd section, a dominating size fraction was oscillating around 5 μ m, with some subtle changes in the sub-dominance of volume concentrations of other size modes, either towards smaller size fractions (T2, T4) or larger ones (T3, T5).

Figure 3.8. Upper panel: Vertical profiles of total volume concentration of particles assessed via LISST along the 2nd section (unified scales). Lower panel: size structure of particles assessed via LISST at the stations along the 2nd section. Y axis: Volume concentrations within 32 size classes normalised to the widths of the size classes. X axis: $\log(\text{size class})$

4. Macrozooplankton, pelagic fish, and acoustics

Cruise participants (in alphabetical order): Frida A. Cnossen^{1,4}, Maxime Geoffroy^{2,3}, Paul Renaud⁴, Einat Sandbank²

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Introduction

Oceanic fronts are defined by steep gradients in physical properties, but it is unresolved how tightly coupled these gradients are to the pelagic community structure across all size ranges and trophic levels. For many biota, the Barents Sea Polar Front represents thermal boundary between warm Atlantic and cold Arctic habitats¹⁻³ leading to variations in species composition, density, and functional traits (such as size and feeding mode) across the Polar Front. However, the Front does not constitute an absolute boundary as organisms are subjected to advection and mixing across frontal zones. Particularly on small scales, fronts and their biological manifestations can be highly dynamic and drifting organisms can be either concentrated or dispersed by the physical processes occurring at the Front. Higher densities of specific plankton size-fractions have been observed in frontal zones⁴⁻⁶ with enhanced eddy formation along frontal zones⁷ leading to patches of elevated plankton concentrations⁶. The Polar Front has been suggested to be an important feeding area for several fish species⁸. Which species aggregate, where and why they do so, and how this varies seasonally, however, is poorly understood. The main aim of the macrozooplankton, pelagic fish, and acoustics sampling is to define changes in terms of species composition, distribution, abundance, and biomass across the front. We relate this variability to the physical properties of the frontal structure. We also document stomach contents and lipid concentrations in fish to assess how these intermediate trophic levels contribute to the flow of energy across ecosystem (e.g., wasp-waist control)⁹. Finally, we will use the broadband acoustic-trawl datasets to classify the frequency-response curves (i.e., acoustic signature) of the dominant taxa.

Methodology

Tucker Trawl

Macrozooplankton were sampled with a Tucker trawl (1 m² opening and 1000 µm mesh size; Figure 1a) towed for 10 minutes at 2 knots. The targeted depth at each station was determined from the epipelagic SSL identified in the echogram from the vessel's echosounder. Relative abundance from the Tucker trawl samples were analysed per station. The length distribution of macrozooplankton was measured from subsamples and each taxa were dried in pre-weighted recipients for dry weight measurements.

Harstad Pelagic Trawl

We deployed a Harstad pelagic trawl (Figure 4.1b) within the sound scattering layer to ground-truth the acoustic signal and sample fish for stomach contents, lipid analyses and stable isotopes. The Harstad trawl had an opening of 18.28 m x 18.28 m and an effective height of 9-11 m and width of 10-12 m at 3 knots. The mesh size of the inner liner of the cod end was 10 mm. The Harstad trawl was towed at ca. 3 knots for 20-30 min. All organisms were identified to species or genus onboard. We recorded the total number and weight of each species.

Hull-mounted EK60

The keel-mounted Simrad EK60[®] split-beam echosounder continuously recorded hydroacoustic data at 18, 38, and 120 kHz. The ping rate was set to 1.5 seconds and pulse length to 1,024 µs. The echosounder was calibrated annually using the standard sphere method (Demer et al., 2015). A Seabird 911 Plus CTD[®] recorded temperature and conductivity regularly throughout the transects from which we could derive profiles of temperature and salinity, sound speed (Mackenzie, 1981), and the coefficient of absorption at each frequency (François and Garrison, 1982).

Acoustic probe (WBAT)

At some stations (Table 1), we deployed an acoustic probe composed of a Wideband Acoustic Transceiver (WBAT; Kongsberg Maritime AS) mounted on the LOPC rosette frame and connected to a sideward-looking 38 kHz split beam transducer (Model ES38-18DK; 36-45 kHz) and a sideward-looking 333 kHz single beam transducer (Model ES333-7CDK-single; 280-380 kHz), both operated in broadband mode split-beam wideband (Figure 1c). The ping rate was set to 1 second, the range to 50 m, the pulse length to 2,048 μ s, and power to 225 W at 38kHz and 38 W at 333 kHz. The WBAT was calibrated in January 2022. The time of the WBAT was synchronized with the LOPC-CTD to extract the exact depth at each ping.

Acoustic analyses

Acoustic data were scrutinized and cleaned with Echoview® 12. We used Echoview’s algorithms to remove background noise, impulse noise, and attenuated noise signals (De Robertis and Higginbottom, 2007; Ryan et al., 2015). A minimum signal to noise ratio threshold of 10 dB was applied. Samples with a lower signal to noise ratio were considered indistinguishable from background noise and were excluded from the analysis with the background noise algorithm

Stomach Contents

Data on the fish diet were obtained through stomach contents based on the availability of species catch from the Harstad pelagic trawl. For large catches, subsamples of 20-30 individuals were taken with representing length distributions of the catch. The standard length, height at the anus (up to the nearest 1mm), and weight (up to the nearest 0.1g) were measured for all specimens in the subsample. The stomachs were isolated and immediately preserved in 70% ethanol, and further analysis on the contents was conducted by trained and experienced personnel. For each individual stomach, the level of fullness (from 0: empty, to 4: full), prey composition (the count and % volume each prey item takes up in the stomach), and the level of digestion for each prey item (from 1: newly eaten, to 5: digested or non-identifiable) were estimated and recorded.

Figure 4.1. (a) Tucker trawl, (b) Harstad pelagic trawl, and (c) acoustic probe deployed during the PolarFront cruise in May 2022.

Table 4.1. Sampling operations conducted by the macrozooplankton, fish, and acoustics team.

Station	Event ID	Date (UTC)	Time (UTC)	Sampling Depth (m)	Sampling Time (min)	Tucker Trawl	Pelagic Trawl	WBAT	Comment
PF1	730	2022-05-19	21:55	22:08	13	x			Used in Meaghan's experiments
PF1	731	2022-05-19	22:28	120	12	x			
PF1	732	2022-05-19	22:58	250	9	x			
PF1	743	2022-05-20	4:32	300	18			x	
PF1	744	2022-05-20	5:23	55-140	30		x		
PF1	744	2022-05-20	5:23	55-140	32		x		
	746	2022-05-20	18:33	287	46			x	
	747	2022-05-20	20:28	300	16			x	
	748	2022-05-20	21:55	290	18			x	
PF2	750	2022-05-21	4:52	271	43			x	
	765	2022-05-21	12:37	280	45			x	
PF2*	766	2022-05-21	14:16	115	9	x			Used in Meaghan's experiments
PF2*	767	2022-05-21	14:45	115	13	x			
PF2*	768	2022-05-21	15:22	230	17?	x			
	769	2022-05-21	16:07	280	43			x	
PF2*	772	2022-05-21	18:31	118-200	27		x		
	774	2022-05-21	19:59	295	50			x	
	778	2022-05-22	0:18	300	48			x	
PF3	781	2022-05-22	5:09	60-100	23		x		
PF3	782	2022-05-22	6:06	340	53			x	
PF3	788	2022-05-22	9:56	60	13	x			Used in Meaghan's experiments
PF3	789	2022-05-22	10:18	60	7	x			
PF3	790	2022-05-22	10:35	120	9	x			
	803	2022-05-22	19:31	350	61			x	
PF4	805	2022-05-23	4:47	70-140	28		x		
PF4	809	2022-05-23	7:48	775	12	x			Empty
PF4	810	2022-05-23	8:11	140	12	x			Empty
PF4	811	2022-05-23	8:42	250	12	x			Used in Meaghan's experiments
PF4	812	2022-05-23	9:19	250	14	x			
PF4	819	2022-05-23	14:43	328	20			x	
	823	2022-05-24	6:49	241	19			x	
	825	2022-05-24	9:14	209	26			x	
	827	2022-05-24	11:11	192	19			x	
	829	2022-05-24	13:42	178	11			x	
PF5	832	2022-05-24	16:19	184	31			x	
PF5	847	2022-05-24	21:23	25	7	x			Used in Meaghan's experiments
PF5	848	2022-05-24	21:35	25	16	x			
PF6*	857	2022-05-25	8:12	180	9	x			Used in Meaghan's experiments
PF6*	857	2022-05-25	8:42	180	10	x			
PF6	866	2022-05-25	11:50	222	36			x	
PF6*	868	2022-05-25	13:16	180	31		x		

*Due to Ice coverage, the trawl was operated at the first open water space south from the original station

Preliminary results

1) High abundance of capelin was observed both on the acoustics (Figure 4.2) and in the nets. Capelin (*Mallotus villosus*) was captured in all Harstad trawl deployments (Figure 4.4ab). The highest density of capelin was at station PF4, where 200kg were sampled in a 20 min trawl. The catch at PF4 was entirely capelin with no other species present (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.2. Example of a hull-mounted EK60 echogram at 18 kHz on 20 May, 2022.

Figure 4.3. Catch of capelin at station PF4.

Figure 4.4. (a) Fish species caught at PF2, (b) length distribution of capelin caught at PF1 (c) biomass of the pelagic and Tucker trawls in catch per minute by station.

2) Polar cod was captured with capelin at the northern stations (PF2, PF3, PF6). The relative abundance of polar cod increased with latitude, with the highest relative abundance at station PF2 (Figure 4.5a).

3) Krill (*Thysanoessa inermis*, *Thysanoessa longicaudata*, and *Meganctiphanes norvegica*, in relative order of abundance) and chaetognaths (*Sagitta elegans* and *Eukrohnia hamata*) comprised a large proportion of the catch at all stations (Figure 4.5b), but in very low abundance where the capelin were abundant. The Arctic station PF5 had the highest biomass (Figure 4.4d) and was mostly dominated by copepods (Figure 4.5b). No krill was sampled in the thick capelin schools at 50-100 m depth, and most krill was rather sampled deeper.

Figure 4.5: (a) relative catch composition from the pelagic trawl, and (b) relative dry weight composition of the zooplankton samples.

4) Except at station PF6, where krill was abundant, stomach content analysis showed that capelin were generally not feeding much and seemed lean (to be confirmed with future lipid concentration analyses). They were mostly caught at depths where macrozooplankton did not occur in high abundances. In contrast, polar cod were feeding at all the stations where they were caught at depths with higher macrozooplankton abundance, and no empty stomachs were found. The main prey items for all fish species were krill and copepods, as well as some teleosts (including capelin) for polar cod.

5) Along the second transect (section 2), the acoustic backscatter was closely correlated with the front, with most biological backscatter remaining in the Atlantic water and low backscatter in the fresher and colder Arctic and melt water. The main exception is a layer of krill and copepods between 50-100 m depth north of the front (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.6: prey composition and stomach fullness of capelin and polar cod across the stations. *S* = small, *M* = medium, *L* = large.

References

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Looking at fish stomachs (Photo: S. Thode)

Figure 4.7. EK60 echograms along section 2 on 23-24 May, 2022.

5. Visual sensitivity of zooplankton

Meaghan Lightfoot, University of Delaware

Visual sensitivity of vertically migratory Arctic zooplankton across the Polar Front was assessed using a filter apparatus to expose animals to various spectra and intensities of light. The objective of this research is to determine the visual sensitivity of key zooplankton species both during the Midnight Sun and Polar Night. Visual system assessments are critical in modeling diel vertical migration, predator-prey relations, and can even help describe greater biological events such as carbon transport. Results can be used to describe visual changes in relation to climate change – loss of sea ice introducing greater illumination into the water column, etc. – and the use of artificial light in the Arctic region.

Zooplankton were sampled at each station using WP3 nets and tucker trawls at various depths. Upon sampling, zooplankton were sorted in a 3 °C dark cold room under red light, after which animals were placed individually in test tubes and transferred in as little light as possible to a preset 2 °C incubator. Animals were given a dark acclimation period of approximately one hour before experimental trials. High intensity light was collimated through two motorized filter wheels connected to a liquid light guide inside the incubator from which animals were exposed to specified light increments of various wavelengths and irradiance levels. Behavioral responses of individuals were recorded on Locomotor Activity Monitors (LAM). Each LAM consists of 32 individual test tube positions, surrounded by three infrared beams to form a beam path. When an animal vertically crosses this path, movement is recorded as a beam break in LAM compatible software.

In spectral experiments, animals were exposed to wavelengths across the visible spectrum, specifically 400 nm to 670 nm, and negative phototaxis was recorded as a proxy for spectral sensitivity. Once spectral sensitivity was determined, zooplankton were exposed to one wavelength (peak sensitivity) at various intensities to determine what irradiance levels elicit a response in such organisms (Response Irradiance experiment). Zooplankton of interest included copepods, such as *Metridia longa* and *Calanus* species, and larger zooplankton: krill (*Thysanoessa longicaudata*, *Thysanoessa raschii*, *Thysanoessa inermis* and *Meganyctiphanes norvegica*), amphipods (*Hyperia galba*, *Themisto*), and chaetognaths (*Parasagitta elegans*). Table 1 describes in detail the zooplankton sampled across the various cruise stations.

Fig. 5.1 Normalized Spectral Sensitivity of *Metridia longa*. Mean movement across the sums of all 79 individual copepods per wavelength plotted with 95% confidence intervals.

Fig. 5.2 Normalized Irradiance Sensitivity of *Metridia longa* at 490 nm. Mean movement across sums of all 58 individual copepods per light intensity plotted with 95% confidence intervals.

Table 5.1. The number of species sampled, and experiments conducted per Polar Front station.

Station	PF1	PF2	PF3	PF4	PF5	PF6
Sampling Method/s	Tucker Trawl (120m) WP3 (Water Column)	Tucker Trawl (115m) WP3 (200m)	Tucker Trawl (60m)	Tucker Trawl (240m)	Tucker Trawl (25m)	Tucker Trawl (180m)
Experiment/s	Spectral	Spectral	Spectral	Spectral Response Irradiance	Spectral	Spectral
Species Tested	<i>Metridia</i> (n = 14) <i>Calanus</i> (n = 2)	Krill (n = 20) <i>Calanus</i> (n = 15) <i>Metridia</i> (n = 11)	Krill (n = 21) <i>Clione</i> (n = 4)	<i>Metridia</i> (n = 82) <i>Calanus</i> (n = 16) Krill (n = 16) Chaetognaths (n = 5)	<i>Calanus</i> (n = 30) <i>Hyperia galba</i> (n = 29) <i>Clione</i> (n = 6) Krill (n = 15)	Krill (n = 23) Chaetognaths (n = 11)

*n = animals that exhibited movement and are viable for analysis

At PF4 specifically, *Metridia longa* exhibited high behavioral sensitivity to 490 nm (Fig. 1). A response irradiance experiment was conducted to determine what intensity threshold elicits a response from *Metridia* individuals at 490 nm (Fig 5.2).

Taking pictures of organisms after experiments (photo: S. Thode)

6. Glider deployments

*Muriel Dunn (Akvaplan-niva & MUN), Loizos Groutas (Cyprus Subsea Consulting & Services),
Virginie Ramasco (Akvaplan-niva), Marie Porter (SAMS)*

Introduction

A fleet of gliders was deployed before and during the cruise to extend the spatial and temporal resolution of the data collection. Two autonomous underwater vehicles, Seagliders (Hydroid M1), collected data for hydrography, zooplankton images and broadband hydroacoustic throughout the water column. Additionally, two autonomous surface vehicles, Sailbuoys (Offshore Sensing Ltd.), equipped with acoustic instruments collected data on water velocity and biological backscatter as well as surface hydrography data across the polar front until the 26th of July 2022, extending the data collection period by approx. 2 months

The primary planned mission for the Sailbuoys was to repeat a N-S transect along the 29.5 E latitude going as close to the ice edge, and presumably the polar front, as possible, red line in Figure 6.2. This primary transect was planned to be the same as the research vessel R/V Helmer Hanssen. The secondary transect was selected to cross the front to the west of the first transect for a comparison at a different location across the front, blue line in Figure 6.2.

Deployment and recovery summary

Sailbuoy EK80 (Echo 1 and Iskant)

The Sailbuoy Echo 1 was deployed ahead of the vessel-based cruise campaign. The autonomous surface vehicle was deployed from a fishing vessel April 29th, 2022. The Sailbuoy Echo 1 was demasted during a storm on the May 7th at 22:00 UTC, but continued floating and collecting data until recovery on May 13th. The Sailbuoy Echo 1 was substituted by SB Iskant, which was deployed on May 19th at 17:46 UTC from 74.7 N, 29.41 E using the crane and quick release hook from R/V Helmer Hanssen, Figure 6.2. Data collection settings and sensor information are described in Table 6.1 and 6.2 for the Sailbuoy Echo 1 and Sailbuoy Iskant, respectively. The Sailbuoy Iskant was recovered on July 24th.

Figure 6.1. Sailbuoy Iskant deployment from R/V Helmer Hanssen on May 19th. (Photo: S. Thode)

Figure 6.2. Primary transect (red, all gliders and cruise vessel) - the actual transect was along the 29.5 E longitude, and secondary transect (blue, Sailbuoys only).

Table 6.1. Sailbuoy Echo 1 sensors and data collection information

Sensor	Parameter	Sampling freq./duty cycle	Nr data points recorded or similar
Datalogger (D)	Conductivity, Temperature, EchoTriplet (Fluo), O2	Every 30 min (more often when testing)	541 datapoints
WBT mini + 200kHz split-beam transducer	Acoustic backscatter	On 10 min every 30 min (normal) or 60 minutes (battery saving) Step 6: FM, 185-255 kHz, fast ramping, active, 75W, 2048 us pulse duration	

Table 6.2. Sailbuoy Iskant sensors and data collection information.

Sensor	Parameter	Sampling freq./duty cycle	Nr data points recorded or similar
WBT mini + 200kHz split-beam transducer	Acoustic backscatter (ES200-7CDK)	On 10 min every 30 min Step 2: CW, 200 kHz, active, 75W, 1024 us pulse duration	5971 segments between April 29 th and July 24 th 2022

Sailbuoy ADCP

The Sailbuoy equipped with Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP, Table 6.3) was deployed with the same crab fishing vessel as the Sailbuoy Echo 1 on April 29th, 2022. The ADCP collect data on water velocity. The repeat transects across the front could provide information on water transport along or across the Front. The Sailbuoy ADCP was recovered with the Sailbuoy Iskant.

Table 6.3. Sailbuoy ADCP sensors and data collection settings

Sensor	Parameter	Sampling freq./duty cycle/settings	Nr data points recorded
Datalogger (D)	Lat/long	Every 15 min	
Autopilot (A)	Lat/long	5 – 15 min (depending on pilots)	
ADCP 600 kHz	Current speed/dir	2 min ping interval	

Seaglider (SG644 – University of Cyprus)

The Seaglider SG644 equipped with active acoustics (EK80 WBT mini) and underwater vision profiler (UVP6) was deployed in collaboration with Bioglider (<https://bioglider.eu/>). The recent development of compact, energy efficient activate acoustic instrument (WBT mini) and optical sensor (UVP6) has enabled the installation of these complimentary sensors on an autonomous underwater vehicle. The Seaglider SG644 was deployed from the R/V Helmer Hanssen at 20:25 on May 19th, 2022 at 75.00 N, 29.50 E. Adjustments of the pitch and roll were required to maintain a proper flight trajectory. The compass was calibrated for the high latitudes once deployed. The Seaglider SG644 was successfully recovered on May 26th from the R/V Helmer Hanssen side CTD room using a rope on a long pole, due to waves height of ~2.5m (Figure 6.3). The rope and pole recovery method was a high-risk procedure, **but** necessary due to the weather conditions. The Seaglider was recovered on the third attempt. The WBT mini and 333 kHz single beam transducer was post-calibrated in Tromsø on July 29th, 2022, using a 25 mm sphere for a target strength broadband frequency response analysis, no on/off-axis calibration was possible with single-beam.

Table 6.4. Glider fleet sensor description and deployment and recovery schedule

Sensor	Parameter	Sampling freq./duty cycle	Nr data points recorded or similar
CT	CT	Every 5 secs	172 profiles (86 up, 86 down)
Optode	O2	Every 5 secs	172 profiles (86 up, 86 down)
GPS	Latitude/longitude	Every surfacing	86 dives covering 68.6 km
WBT mini + 333 kHz single beam transducer	Acoustic backscatter	Continuous during descent	86 profiles (down only) (14.5 GB)
UVP6	images	Above 100 m: 2 Hz Below 100 m: 0.5 Hz	172 profiles of images (1.8 GB)
Depth	depth	Dive to seafloor (within 30 m)	30m, 90m, 210m, then 360 m

Figure 6.3. Recovery of Seaglider SG644 with rope and long rope due to rough weather conditions (Photo: ?)

Seaglider (SG153 – Akvaplan-niva)

The environmental Seaglider SG153 was equipped with a wide variety of sensors and a hydrophone for passive acoustic measurements (Table 6.4.) The Seaglider SG644 was deployed from the R/V Helmer Hanssen at 20:54 on May 19th, 2022 at 75.00 N, 29.51 E. Adjustments of the pitch and roll were required to maintain a proper flight trajectory. The compass was calibrated for the high-latitude mission once deployed. Unfortunately, a malfunction with the buoyancy system required that the glider be recovered and shortened the expected deployment time. After the completing 5 dives, the Seaglider SG153 was successfully recovered on May 20th with the MOB boat and crane.

Table 6.5. *Sensor description on the Seaglider SG153*

Sensor	Parameter	Sampling freq./duty cycle	Nr data points recorded or similar
CT	Conductivity and temperature	Every 5 secs	9 profiles (5 up, 4 down)
GPS	Latitude/longitude	Every surfacing	5 dives and 1.65 km (see KML)
SeaOwl	Chla, FDOM, backscatter	Every 10 secs	9 profiles (5 up, 4 down)
PAR	Photosynthetic active radiation	Every 10 secs	9 profiles (5 up, 4 down)
Hydrophone	sound	continuously	2.1 GB continuous for 9 profiles (5 up, 4 down)
Depth	depth	Dive to seafloor	Dives to 30m, 100m, 250 m

Preliminary results

Sailbuoys (ADCP, Echo 1 and Iskant)

The Sailbuoys completed their missions in the spring and summer in Barents Sea between April 29th, 2022 and July 26th 2022. Their transects are shown in Figure 6.4.

Figure 6.4 The transects of the Sailbuoys during the spring and summer 2022 field campaign. Panel A shows the full extent down to Northern Norway with the zoomed in extent of the B panel shown in red.

Seaglider SG644

Seaglider 644 ran a successful mission completing 86 dives during the 8-day survey in the Barents Sea in an area of ~370 m depth (Figure 6.4). The trajectory started at the north-eastern extent in Figure 6.x on May 19th and ended in the southwestern extent on May 26th. The data from this mission had the software-derived quality control added, with data marked “no change” to “probably good” accepted. A more thorough quality control including manual despiking is yet to be carried out. The data are also yet to be calibrated. CTD profiles were collected on board the Helmer Hansen to allow for cross calibration and these must be applied before the data are used further.

Figure 6.5. *The location of each dive plotted at the average latitude and longitude.*

Here we show some basic representations of the hydrographic properties (Figure 6.5), where we find the density gradient increased at 100 m depth after May 23rd.

Figure 6.6. Temperature salinity and density data collected by the glider during all the dives collated over time.

Below is an example of the data after gridding with an objective analysis gridding method.

Figure 6.7. Salinity data, gridded by time, in longitude, latitude with pressure curtain on y-axis (pressure in dbar). Colorbar units are PSU.

Initial observations from the glider data suggest that it passed through a cold/fresh eddy between 75° N and 74.9° N at approximately 29.1° E. This is corroborated by satellite SST (Aqua/Modis; Minnett, 2004) which shows a cold feature at this location on May 24th, 2022 (Figure 6.8).

Figure 6.8. SST on the 24th May 2022 taken from the Aqua/Modis satellite

The EK80 WBT mini integration on the Seaglider SG644 was successful and resulted in 178 raw data files. Most dives showed an aggregation of targets starting between 50 and 100 m below the transducer (Figure 6.x starting at 70 m until the aggregation reached 5-20 m at 21:40). As the seaglider descended in the water column, the aggregations got closer to the echosounder until the echosounder collected data within the school which resulted in clear discrete targets. As the seaglidings kept diving deeper, the seafloor (bright yellow band on a diagonal between 22:00 and 22:15 in Figure 6.9) appears and gradually approaches the transducer face.

Figure 6.9. Echosounder backscatter data from a dive with the Seaglider. This dive was on May 22nd 2022 between 21:25 and 22:15.

Seaglider SG153

The passive acoustics Seaglider completed 5 dives (green in Figure 6.x) recording the hydrographic data shown in Figure 6.x The hydrophone AMAR G4 data were pre-processed for assessing file duration and noise content. We observed a large amount of noise for the duration of the five dives, in relation to the proximity to the support vessel, and no biological signal sources. However, due to the limited number of dives and the inconsistent date-time labels for each audio file and dive folder, the files were not processed further.

Figure 6.10. Temperature salinity and density data collected by the glider (SG153) during all the dives collated over time.

References:

MODIS_AQUA_L3_SST_THERMAL_DAILY_4KM_DAYTIME_V2019.0 doi:10.5067/MODSA-1D4D9; Details of the algorithm can be found at Ocean Biology Processing Group (OBPG/OB.DAAC) website.

P. J. Minnett et al., "Sea-surface temperature measurements from the Moderate-Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) on Aqua and Terra," IGARSS 2004. 2004 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, Anchorage, AK, 2004, pp. 4576-4579 vol.7. doi: 10.1109/IGARSS.2004.1370173.

7. Visual surveys of mammals and sea birds

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Introduction

Top-predators such as sea mammals and birds are key indicators of ocean health. Due to their position at the top of the food web, variations in abundance, distribution, and nutrient content at lower trophic levels will be reflected in marine predator behaviour, distribution, and health. Monitoring the occurrence of these animal groups is therefore vital for understanding cumulative changes across the trophic networks.

The Barents Sea polar front, as a transition zone from warm and saline Atlantic water to cold and less dense Arctic water, is an area of high productivity with a large diversity of animal groups from different trophic levels. The Polar Front has been suggested to be an important feeding area for several fish species¹, making it an attractive region for marine predators. Several marine mammal aggregations have been reported in the area², though little is known about their occurrence outside the summer months.

We therefore aimed at monitoring marine mammal and sea bird occurrence throughout the field expedition in May 2022 (18th to the 28th), as the first top-predator survey of the PolarFront project. The results will provide new insights on animal occurrence and species diversity for the spring season, while overcoming some of the current data availability limitations.

Methods

Two observers performed visual surveys from the bridge deck of RV Helmer Hansen. The observers systematically scanned the area around the vessel, usually alternating scan sweeps with binoculars, monitoring and the naked eye 180 degrees ahead of the vessel throughout transiting periods, *i.e.*, not during station work. To avoid observer exhaustion, a duty cycle was designed, which also ensured even sampling coverage (in hours). Each survey consisted of one monitoring hour, followed by two hours of break. The observers scanned the horizon for animal cues (e.g., whale blow) using a combination of naked eye and binoculars, starting from 4AM and until at 8PM (time zone: UTC). No observations were made during Beaufort Sea state conditions above 5.

On-watch data was recorded on data sheets, following data protocols. Effort data forms were compiled for each watch, recording sightability and wind force information. For each animal observation, we recorded date, time, species, behaviour, number of individuals, and GPS coordinates on sightings data forms. Individual mammals were identified using identification cues, such as blow and shape of dorsal fin. In cases where cues are limited, the identification was made to the nearest Family or Order for both seabirds and marine mammals. Observations made during off-effort time were also included, though they do not reflect systematic sampling. The recordings were initiated as the research vessel sailed from Tromsø and the observers were allowed to occupy the bridge.

Results

We monitored a total of 50.2 hours and identified a variety of different mammal and seabird species. Of those, 17 hours were conducted in transit and during Sea State equal or lower than 4. Overall, Sea state conditions varied between Sea state 0 and 5, with an average of 3 in the Beaufort scale (see figure 1), with low percentages of glare (<12%), though large cloud cover. Nevertheless, light and visibility conditions were on average good, ranging between periods of heavy rain to periods of clear visibility to the horizon. Though no dedicated observations were made during Sea states above 5, we did record sporadic and extraordinary sightings (e.g., species with distinct cues and in the vicinity of the ship).

Due to station work timelines, observer duty often coincided with local sampling stations, and it was decided to maintain the schedule to ensure systematic sampling rather than operating solely on periods of transit.

Figure 7.1. Daily variation in mean Beaufort Sea State conditions between May 18th and May 23rd

Seabirds

We report sightings corresponding to estimates that exclude ship following species, such as the kittiwake (*Rissa tridactyla*) and the fulmar (*Fulmarus glacialis*). Throughout the expedition period, we recorded 17 different identifiable species of seabirds (table 1), with the majority of the animals being Guillemot (*Uria* sp.). We estimate a total of 1593 individual animals between the 18th and the 24th of May, with occurrence both on ice, in seawater, and flying (Figure 7.2). *Uria* sp. was also the only seabird group to be recorded resting on sea ice floes.

Figure 7.2. Boxplot of daily numbers of seabirds. The blue shaded area indicates presence of sea ice during the survey time.

Table 7.1. Number of seabird sights per species recorded between the 18th and the 24th of May 2022

Species	Flying	Water	Ice
<i>Alca torda</i>	12	2	0
<i>Alle alle</i>	0	7	0
<i>Cephus grylle</i>	24	8	0
<i>Fratercula arctica</i>	12	25	0
<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	1	0	0
<i>Fulmarus sp.</i>	4	2	0
<i>Larus canus</i>	1	0	0
<i>Larus fuscus</i>	5	0	0
<i>Larus hyperboreus</i>	7	0	0
<i>Larus marinus</i>	2	0	0
<i>Larus sp.</i>	2	0	0
<i>Pagophila eburnea</i>	4	0	0
<i>Passeridae</i>	1	0	0
<i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>	1	0	0
<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	12	0	0
<i>Stercorarius parasiticus</i>	2	0	0
<i>Stercorarius pomarinus</i>	2	0	0
<i>Stercorarius skua</i>	2	0	0
<i>Uria aalge</i>	113	25	0
<i>Uria lomvia</i>	30	17	2
<i>Uria sp.</i>	840	404	24

Mammals

We identified 6 different species of marine mammals (see table 2, figure 3). The largest number of detections corresponds to the Delphinidae family. We observed an additional large number of humpback and minke whales (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata* and *Balaenoptera novaeangliae*), across different survey locations. That is, we did not identify a particular spatial pattern for their occurrence (See figure 4), other than possibly a 300 m isobath limiting the shallowest depths at which all species were found.

Table 7.2. Number of marine mammal sightings per species between the 18th and the 24rd of May 2022.

Species	Number
<i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i>	8
<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	1
<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	9
<i>Cetacea</i>	3
<i>Orcinus orca</i>	2
<i>Lagenorhynchus albirostris</i>	4
<i>Delphinidae</i>	48
<i>Pagophilus groenlandicus</i>	2
<i>Pinnipeds</i>	2

Figure 7.3. Number of detections of each species between May 18th and May 22nd of the field expedition

Figure 7.4. Map of the geographic distribution of the marine mammal species recorded

Conclusions

These first results provide measures of species diversity and geographic distribution during a period of the year with limited data available in the Barents Sea. The diversity of both mammal and seabird species indicates the richness of the region to sustain high trophic levels.

References

- ¹Lien VS (ed). 2018. *Fisken og Havet 8-2018*. 75 pp.
- ²Skern-Mauritzen M et al. 2011

Outreach & Publication

Senior adviser in research communication *Sunniva Thode* from UiT joined the cruise and wrote a number of blogs:

https://uit.no/nyheter/artikkel?p_document_id=773834

https://uit.no/nyheter/artikkel/kortnytt?p_document_id=774849

https://uit.no/nyheter/artikkel/kortnytt?p_document_id=777748

<https://blogg.uit.no/bfebackstage/2022/05/19/polarfront-project-on-their-way-to-unveil-the-mysteries-of-the-polar-front-in-the-barents-sea/>

<https://forskning.no/arktisk-havet-partner/hvorfor-er-det-sa-lite-hoppekreps-her/2043744>

Frida Cnossen finished her master thesis at the Universite Côte D’Azur in July 2022 based on data collected during this cruise:

“Macrozooplankton Distribution and Feeding Ecology of Planktivorous Fish at the Barents Sea Polar Front”

Appendix: Sample log

<u>Event#</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Latitude (N) decimals</u>	<u>Longitude (E) decimals</u>	<u>Bottom depth (m)</u>	<u>Sampling date (UTC)</u>	<u>Sampling time UTC (start)</u>	<u>Gear</u>	<u>Sampling depth (m) from</u>	<u>Sampling depth (m) to</u>	<u>Sample type</u>	<u>Sample staff</u>	<u>Preservation method</u>
726		74.70	29.41	379	19.05.2022	17:46:42	Sail buoy deployment					
727		75.00	29.50	372	19.05.2022	20:25:31	GLIDER- deployment				Loizos	
728		75.00	29.51	372	19.05.2022	20:54:19	GLIDER- deployment				Loizos	
729	PF1	75.01	29.50	373	19.05.2022	21:24:09	CTD with water				Eva	
730	PF1	75.01	29.52	370	19.05.2022	21:55:24	Tucker Trawl	120		experiments	Meaghan	not kept
731	PF1	75.01	29.59	372	19.05.2022	22:28:48	Tucker Trawl	140		abundance, biomass	Paul	dry weight
732	PF1	75.01	29.61	372	19.05.2022	22:56:36	Tucker Trawl	250		abundance, biomass	Paul	dry weight
733	PF1	75.01	29.51	371	19.05.2022	23:24:58	CTD with water				Eva	
734	PF1	75.01	29.52	372	19.05.2022	23:54:05	Multinet	352	200	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
734	PF1	75.01	29.52	372	19.05.2022	23:54:05	Multinet	200	100	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
734	PF1	75.01	29.52	372	19.05.2022	23:54:05	Multinet	100	50	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
734	PF1	75.01	29.52	372	19.05.2022	23:54:05	Multinet	50	20	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
734	PF1	75.01	29.52	372	19.05.2022	23:54:05	Multinet	20	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
735	PF1	75.01	29.53	370	20.05.2022	00:37:04	FRRF				Rolf	
736	PF1	75.01	29.53	371	20.05.2022	00:56:49	Phytoplankton				Rolf	
737	PF1	75.01	29.53	370	20.05.2022	01:05:54	FRRF				Rolf	
738	PF1	75.01	29.53	372	20.05.2022	01:20:46	CTD with water				Eva	
739	PF1	75.01	29.53	371	20.05.2022	02:11:47	WP2	360	0	biomass	Malin	dry weight
740	PF1	75.01	29.54	371	20.05.2022	02:45:03	WP3	360	0	lipids	Malin	images
741	PF1	75.01	29.55	373	20.05.2022	03:20:27	WP3	100	0	Eggproduction	Torkel	no Calanus
742	PF1	75.01	29.56	374	20.05.2022	03:34:37	WP3	360	0	Eggproduction	Torkel	
743	PF1	75.01	29.59	373	20.05.2022	04:32:28	LOPC /Frankenstein	360	0		Sünnje, Max, Emilia	
744	PF1	75.01	29.57	375	20.05.2022	05:23:06	Pelagic trawl	55, 140		composition, abundance	Max	stomachs in ethanol
745	Transect	74.99	29.54	376	20.05.2022	06:56:30	MVP START				Sünnje	
746	Transect	75.96	29.50	299	20.05.2022	18:25:42	LOPC /Frankenstein	287			Sünnje	
747	Transect	76.04	29.50	309	20.05.2022	20:12:26	LOPC /Frankenstein	300			Sünnje	
748	Transect	76.10	29.49	304	20.05.2022	21:42:46	LOPC /Frankenstein	290			Sünnje	
749	Transect	76.15	29.35	274	21.05.2022	04:06:30	FrrF				Rolf	
749	PF2	76.15	29.35	274	21.05.2022	04:06:30	FrrF				Rolf	
750	PF2	76.15	29.37	280	21.05.2022	04:48:33	LOPC /Frankenstein	271			Sünnje	
751	PF2	76.15	29.38	282	21.05.2022	05:53:06	CTD with water				Eva	
752	PF2	76.15	29.38	282	21.05.2022	05:58:11	CTD with water				Eva	

753	PF2	76.15	29.39	283	21.05.2022	06:38:19	Multinet	262	200	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
753	PF2	76.15	29.39	283	21.05.2022	06:38:19	Multinet	200	100	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
753	PF2	76.15	29.39	283	21.05.2022	06:38:19	Multinet	100	50	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
753	PF2	76.15	29.39	283	21.05.2022	06:38:19	Multinet	50	20	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
753	PF2	76.15	29.39	283	21.05.2022	06:38:19	Multinet	20	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
754	PF2	76.16	29.40	285	21.05.2022	07:01:55	FrrF				Rolf	
755	PF2	76.16	29.40	287	21.05.2022	07:19:02	Phytoplankton				Eva	
756	PF2	76.16	29.40	287	21.05.2022	07:31:41	WP2	260	0	biomass	Malin	dry weight
757	PF2	76.16	29.41	287	21.05.2022	07:59:40	CTD with water				Eva	
758	PF2	76.16	29.41	282	21.05.2022	09:04:22	WP3	260	0	lipids	Malin	images
759	PF2	76.16	29.40	280	21.05.2022	09:55:24	WP3	260	0	experiments	Meaghan	
760	PF2	76.16	29.39	279	21.05.2022	10:05:41	WP3	100	0	Eggproduction	Torkel	
761	PF2	76.16	29.39	279	21.05.2022	10:06:59	FrrF				Rolf	
762	PF2	76.17	29.39	277	21.05.2022	10:24:43	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
763	PF2	76.17	29.38	274	21.05.2022	11:00:50	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
764	Transect	76.08	29.38	295	21.05.2022	12:14:23	FrrF				Rolf	
765	Transect	76.09	29.37	291	21.05.2022	12:36:51	LOPC /Frankenstein	280			Sünnje	
766	Transect	76.05	29.37	297	21.05.2022	14:12:48	Tucker Trawl	115		Meaghans experiments	Meaghan	
767	Transect	76.05	29.33	288	21.05.2022	14:46:55	Tucker Trawl	115		biomass	Max	dry weight
768	Transect	76.05	29.34	292	21.05.2022	15:29:00	Tucker Trawl	230		biomass	Max	dry weight
769	Transect	76.05	29.32	284	21.05.2022	16:08:46	LOPC /Frankenstein	280			Sünnje	
770	Transect	76.00	29.40	291	21.05.2022	17:01:44	FrrF	90			Rolf	
771	Transect	76.00	29.41	289	21.05.2022	17:18:06	LOPC				Sünnje	
772	Transect	75.98	29.52	306	21.05.2022	18:31:59	Pelagic trawl	118, 200		biomass	Max	stomachs in ethanol
773	Transect	75.92	29.62	305	21.05.2022	19:34:12	FrrF				Rolf	
774	Transect	75.92	29.63	306	21.05.2022	19:59:50	LOPC /Frankenstein	295			Sünnje	
775	PF2.5	75.94	29.61	300	21.05.2022	21:07:08	WP2	290	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
776	PF2.5	75.94	29.61	300	21.05.2022	21:31:19	WP3	290	0	lipids	Malin	images
777	PF2.5	75.83	29.58	307	21.05.2022	22:44:27	LOPC				Sünnje	
778	Transect	75.75	29.55	313	22.05.2022	00:18:51	LOPC /Frankenstein	300			Sünnje	
779	Transect	75.83	29.55	303	22.05.2022	01:33:07	LOPC				Sünnje	
780	PF3	75.49	29.53	348	22.05.2022	04:31:59	FrrF	90			Rolf	
781	PF3	75.49	29.56	0	22.05.2022	05:09:47	Pelagic trawl	60, 100			Max	stomachs in ethanol
782	PF3	75.48	29.60	350	22.05.2022	06:06:45	LOPC /Frankenstein	340			Sünnje	
783	PF3	75.48	29.63	353	22.05.2022	07:18:07	CTD with water				Eva	
784	PF3	75.47	29.65	355	22.05.2022	07:47:10	Multinet	335	200	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
784	PF3	75.47	29.65	355	22.05.2022	07:47:10	Multinet	200	100	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
784	PF3	75.47	29.65	355	22.05.2022	07:47:10	Multinet	100	50	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
784	PF3	75.47	29.65	355	22.05.2022	07:47:10	Multinet	50	20	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
784	PF3	75.47	29.65	355	22.05.2022	07:47:10	Multinet	20	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
785	PF3	75.47	29.68	358	22.05.2022	08:46:55	FrrF				Rolf	
786	PF3	75.47	29.69	357	22.05.2022	09:04:19	Phytoplankton				Eva	
787	PF3	75.47	29.70	355	22.05.2022	09:14:27	CTD with water				Eva	

788	PF3	75.46	29.74	359	22.05.2022	09:56:04	Tucker Trawl	60		Meaghan experiment	Meaghan	
789	PF3	75.46	29.77	364	22.05.2022	10:18:56	Tucker Trawl	60		biomass	Max	dry weight
790	PF3	75.45	29.79	348	22.05.2022	10:35:12	Tucker Trawl	120		biomass	Max	dry weight
791	PF3	75.44	29.80	364	22.05.2022	10:52:32	WP2	350	0	biomass	Malin	dry weight
792	PF3	75.44	29.81	364	22.05.2022	11:25:47	WP3	350	0	picking	Malin	not kept
793	PF3	75.44	29.83	361	22.05.2022	12:09:46	WP3	350	0	lipids	Malin	images
794	PF3	75.44	29.84	362	22.05.2022	12:32:48	FrrF				Rolf	
795	PF3	75.44	29.84	360	22.05.2022	12:49:22	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
796	PF3	75.44	29.84	362	22.05.2022	13:10:33	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
797	PF3.5	75.25	29.45	348	22.05.2022	14:56:58	FrrF				Rolf	
798	PF3.5	75.25	29.45	349	22.05.2022	15:19:52	WP2	340	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
799	PF4	75.00	29.02	360	22.05.2022	17:34:16	FrrF				Rolf	
800	PF4	75.00	29.02	360	22.05.2022	17:50:45	CTD no water					
801	PF4	75.00	29.02	360	22.05.2022	18:30:11	WP2	345	0	biomass	Malin	dry weight
802	PF4	75.00	29.04	360	22.05.2022	19:08:13	Multinet	342	200	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
802	PF4	75.00	29.04	360	22.05.2022	19:08:13	Multinet	200	100	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
802	PF4	75.00	29.04	360	22.05.2022	19:08:13	Multinet	100	50	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
802	PF4	75.00	29.04	360	22.05.2022	19:08:13	Multinet	50	20	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
802	PF4	75.00	29.04	360	22.05.2022	19:08:13	Multinet	20	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
803	PF4	75.00	29.05	362	22.05.2022	19:39:05	LOPC /Frankenstein	350			Sünnje	WBAT
804	PF4	75.00	28.99	361	23.05.2022	04:04:33	FrrF	90			Rolf	
805	PF4	74.98	29.01	369	23.05.2022	04:47:29	Pelagic trawl	70, 140			Max	stomachs in ethanol
806	PF4	75.00	29.02	359	23.05.2022	06:04:57	CTD with water				Eva	
807	PF4	75.00	29.03	360	23.05.2022	06:27:06	FrrF	90			Rolf	
808	PF4	75.00	29.05	362	23.05.2022	07:11:56	CTD with water				Eva	
809	PF4	74.99	29.06	363	23.05.2022	07:43:41	Tucker Trawl	75			Paul	
810	PF4	74.98	29.08	365	23.05.2022	08:05:56	Tucker Trawl	140			Paul	
811	PF4	74.97	29.09	367	23.05.2022	08:32:37	Tucker Trawl	250		Meaghan experiment	Meaghan	
812	PF4	74.95	29.12	370	23.05.2022	09:07:48	Tucker Trawl	250		abundance, biomass	Paul	dry weight
813	PF4	74.93	29.15	376	23.05.2022	09:58:35	WP3	360		lipids	Malin	
814	PF4	74.93	29.16	378	23.05.2022	10:25:50	WP3	360		egg production	Torkel	
815	PF4	74.93	29.16	376	23.05.2022	10:55:33	FrrF				Rolf	
816	PF4	74.93	29.16	375	23.05.2022	11:12:07	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
817	PF4	74.93	29.16	378	23.05.2022	11:26:54	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
818	Transect	75.17	29.00	347	23.05.2022	13:14:56	LOPC				Sünnje	
819	Transect	75.33	29.00	340	23.05.2022	14:36:24	LOPC/Frankenstein	328			Sünnje	
820	Transect	75.41	28.99	333	23.05.2022	16:03:02	MVP START				Sünnje	
821	Transect	76.71	29.52	248	24.05.2022	04:33:01	LOPC				Sünnje	
822	Transect	76.80	29.49	267	24.05.2022	05:32:23	LOPC				Sünnje	
823	Transect	76.88	29.51	257	24.05.2022	06:36:59	LOPC/Frankenstein	241			Sünnje	
824	Transect	76.97	29.52	237	24.05.2022	08:00:44	LOPC				Sünnje	
825	Transect	77.06	29.53	218	24.05.2022	09:10:13	LOPC	209			Sünnje	
826	Transect	77.13	29.51	208	24.05.2022	10:03:57	LOPC				Sünnje	

827	Transect	77.21	29.51	203	24.05.2022	11:11:14	LOPC/Frankenstein	192			Sünnje	
828	Transect	77.29	29.49	183	24.05.2022	12:18:28	LOPC				Sünnje	
829	Transect	77.37	29.57	188	24.05.2022	13:34:32	LOPC/Frankenstein	178			Sünnje	
830	Transect	77.46	29.82	202	24.05.2022	15:09:29	LOPC				Sünnje	
831	PF5	77.49	29.86	197	24.05.2022	15:55:06	FrrF	90			Sünnje	
832	PF5	77.49	29.86	196	24.05.2022	16:19:04	LOPC/Frankenstein	184			Sünnje	
833	PF5	77.50	29.85	196	24.05.2022	17:02:47	CTD with water				Eva	
834	PF5	77.50	29.86	194	24.05.2022	17:25:19	Multinet	178	100	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
834	PF5	77.50	29.86	194	24.05.2022	17:25:19	Multinet	100	50	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
834	PF5	77.50	29.86	194	24.05.2022	17:25:19	Multinet	50	20	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
834	PF5	77.50	29.86	194	24.05.2022	17:25:19	Multinet	20	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
835	PF5	77.50	29.86	193	24.05.2022	17:58:14	FrrF	90			Rolf	
836	PF5	77.51	29.87	194	24.05.2022	18:17:52	Phytoplankton				Eva	
837	PF5	77.51	29.87	197	24.05.2022	18:25:13	CTD with water				Eva	
838	PF5	77.51	29.87	200	24.05.2022	18:37:00	WP2	180	0	biomass	Malin	dry weight
839	PF5	77.52	29.87	200	24.05.2022	19:10:54	WP3	190		egg production	Malin	
840	PF5	77.52	29.86	202	24.05.2022	19:31:38	WP3	190		lipids	Malin	
841	PF5	77.52	29.86	202	24.05.2022	19:48:34	WP3	190		live samples	Malin	
842	PF5	77.53	29.87	199	24.05.2022	20:11:25	WP3	190		live samples	Malin	
843	PF5	77.53	29.87	199	24.05.2022	20:11:32	WP3	190		live samples	Malin	
844	PF5	77.53	29.87	196	24.05.2022	20:27:35	FrrF	90			Rolf	
845	PF5	77.54	29.87	196	24.05.2022	20:43:18	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
846	PF5	77.54	29.87	197	24.05.2022	20:55:43	Van Veen Grab				Joel	
847	PF5	77.54	29.95	199	24.05.2022	21:20:35	Tucker trawl	25		Meaghan experiment	Meaghan	
848	PF5	77.54	29.99	203	24.05.2022	21:36:05	Tucker trawl	25		abundance, biomass	Paul	dry weight
849	PF6	77.04	29.52	224	25.05.2022	04:13:10	FrrF	90			Rolf	
850	PF6	77.03	29.53	229	25.05.2022	05:59:28	FrrF	90			Rolf	
851	PF6	77.03	29.53	229	25.05.2022	06:16:02	CTD with water				Eva	
852	PF6	77.03	29.53	228	25.05.2022	06:32:41	Multinet					hit bottom, not kept
853	PF6	77.04	29.53	229	25.05.2022	07:03:31	Phytoplankton				Eva	
854	PF6	77.04	29.53	229	25.05.2022	07:10:20	FrrF	90			Rolf	
855	PF6	77.04	29.54	229	25.05.2022	07:27:20	Multinet	200	150	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
855	PF6	77.04	29.54	229	25.05.2022	07:27:20	Multinet	150	100	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
855	PF6	77.04	29.54	229	25.05.2022	07:27:20	Multinet	100	50	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
855	PF6	77.04	29.54	229	25.05.2022	07:27:20	Multinet	50	20	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
855	PF6	77.04	29.54	229	25.05.2022	07:27:20	Multinet	20	0	composition, abundance	Malin	4% Formalin
856	PF6	77.04	29.54	229	25.05.2022	08:02:18	Tucker Trawl	180		Meaghan experiment	Meaghan	
857	PF6	77.04	29.54	230	25.05.2022	08:02:37	Tucker Trawl	180		abundance, biomass	Paul	dry weight
858	PF6	77.02	29.59	226	25.05.2022	09:09:07	CTD with water				Eva	
859	PF6	77.02	29.61	226	25.05.2022	09:48:07	Phytoplankton				Eva	
860	PF6	77.02	29.61	225	25.05.2022	09:54:07	WP2	219	0	biomass	Malin	dry weight
861	PF6	77.02	29.62	229	25.05.2022	10:12:54	WP2	220	0	egg rproduction	Malin	
862	PF6	77.02	29.63	231	25.05.2022	10:29:18	WP2	220	0	egg production	Malin	

863	PF6	77.02	29.64	232	25.05.2022	10:44:33	WP2	220	0	lipids	Malin	
864	PF6	77.02	29.66	232	25.05.2022	11:10:31	WP2	220	0	stable isotopes	Malin	
865	PF6	77.02	29.68	230	25.05.2022	11:26:28	WP2	220	0	live samples	Malin	
866	PF6	77.02	29.69	234	25.05.2022	11:50:32	LOPC/Frankenstein	222			Sünnje	
867		77.01	29.72	235	25.05.2022	12:35:08	FrrF	90			Rolf	
868		76.99	29.76	233	25.05.2022	13:16:37	Pelagic trawl	180			Max	stomachs in ethanol
869		71.43	22.22	343	27.05.2022	09:05:33	WP3	320	0	live samples	Malin	